

Outcomes from “The Power of Materials Modelling for Industrial Applications” Workshop

Ilian Todorov

*Computational Science and Engineering Division, Scientific Computing Department
STFC Daresbury Laboratory, Sci-Tech Daresbury, Daresbury, WA4 4AD, United Kingdom
email: ilian.todorov@stfc.ac.uk ; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7275-1784>*

Abstract

This article outlines the purpose of the workshop – to gather evidence of the value of materials and molecular modelling for industrial applications, and identify directly the needs and challenges of the industrial partners in the process of their adoption of modelling and simulation as part of their research and development plans.

Workshop Summary

The workshop was held at the Henry Royce Institute in Manchester on 8-9 November 2022, and organised and sponsored by CCP5 and CCP5++ network, the High End Computing Materials Chemistry Consortium, the Henry Royce Institute, the Atomic Weapons Establishment (AWE) and the Scientific Computing Department (SCD) at the Science and Technology Facilities Council (UKRI STFC).

The aim of this workshop is to:

- share knowledge and awareness of the materials modelling endeavours supported by CCP5 that are of benefit to UK PLC,
- hear from our industrial partners (see programme) how they have applied shared modelling and simulation knowledge in their R&D and what impact this has brought to their industry to address real world challenges in materials research, and
- the opportunity to speak to our scientists and lead methodology developers to investigate how the CCP5 know-how and body of knowledge could be used to advance industrial R&D for your organisation.

Who is the event for:

This introductory event is targeted at a wide range of attendees from across industries. The objectives of the meeting are to showcase the predictive capabilities of molecular modelling techniques and to discuss the current and potential opportunities that simulation methodologies can offer for materials discovery and process optimization in an industrial context.

Overview of the event:

The meeting will be held over two days with the first day being devoted to showcasing successful examples of the integration of simulations machine learning and experiments taken from a wide range of industrial applications. Examples will be drawn from across the full breadth of simulation

methodologies spanning from ab initio through atomistic to mesoscopic techniques highlighting how such approaches can be effectively applied to address scientific questions of direct importance to industry and provide computationally derived experimental data and materials insight.

The second day will provide an opportunity for attendees to meet with experts in the field and discuss novel ways in which simulation software can be applied to solve real world problems and explore the current barriers preventing a broader adoption of such techniques in an industrial context. Attendees are encouraged to bring along potential problems/challenges for discussion. The discussion will also look to explore available mechanisms to enable public-private collaborations and software development opportunities in the area of materials simulations.

Main Findings

- UK universities and academic work are more visible than that of STFC.
- Phone and emails queries by industrial attendees to the Royce Institute and the Hartree Centre have not been followed up.
- The attendees with industrial background or project involvement identified three types of companies:
 - Type 1 – already undertaking modelling and providing successful outputs.
 - Those companies that have modelling and simulation (MS) as part of their R&D already know the value (see, develop further and exploit). *They do not share Dos and Don'ts (giving themselves a competitive advantage but also opening the opportunities to other parties – communities, academia, Hartree Centre).*
 - Type 2 – believe that modelling is a suitable tool to help them to support their activities but are not sure who / what to do. *These are our 'customers'.*
 - Those companies that have just ventured in modelling and simulation (MS) and are developing their R&D but lack the preconditioning. They need help with everything and are lacking knowledge, access and assistance.
 - Knowledge of what is possible and breaking down the industrial challenge in a tractable set of suitable problems to tackled on different scales and what they can point to. This could be facilitated by external translators. Where and how to find such – PORTAL/FORUM/MARKETPLACE or via a BID contact? Translation of industrial modelling requirements into actionable modelling activities, *cf.* in the technology world a 'Product Manager' who translates between the customer requirements and product development team.
 - Access to FAIR and well described, centralised data, methods/software – relevant data beyond google, Wikipedia or papers. Structured, open, knowledge base of materials' properties information and relevant policies. Software – coarse graining of methodology (length, time, level, error).
 - Assistance by BIDs who are responsive to calls and can set up meetings with relevant parties. However, this is not enough as the **human portal** is not 24/7? Hence the open question of 'How do we facilitate matchmaking?' between industry and modelling experts (academia, RTO, expertise/software houses).
 - PORTAL/FORUM/MARKETPLACE to publish challenges or find out who has invested in tackling such or is at the brink to take on these with publicly funded effort. Portal entry point – *'I want to calculate x'.*
 - Type 3 – still unaware of modelling and the potential benefits that application of modelling techniques might provide in support of their activities. *These are our potential 'customers'.*

- Many, especially SMEs have no R&D resource or allocation. They are in need of awareness and netting at sandpits by suitable event promoters such as UK's KTN, CPI, Hartree Centre, the Royce Institute.
 - A high-level PORTAL like front door is needed for redirection to further communication or knowledge (but in a better form than Google, Wikipedia or papers can accessibly offer).
- Industry is willing to co-invest but to do that they require to share the risk with a trusted party. Their main need is translation – a trusted service that will expose the design space and reduce it effectively to their benefit:
 - Translation of industrial engineering to molecular simulation is not straightforward and requires discussion and facilitators for it.
 - Need to identify computable proxies of experimental observables in order to enable success via application of modelling tools. This could be the ML space.
 - Consideration of data curation and ensuring onward access. Data curation is not just about converting between document file types but also modelling file types.
 - Also consider activity wrt PSDI on data / code availability and whether this has a role to play as currently outlined or whether the activity could be 'augmented'.
 - How to identify the right technique. How about having a version of the size / length graph which then highlights the properties that are available to be calculated by that technique this would then enable the interested party to at least focus in on the area of interest and direct further investigations.
 - Consideration of whether some type of activity like 'Kaggle' (SANDPITS) where the question is how to calculate a diffusion coefficient in x and people develop ways to do that as per Kaggle / ML events.

Main Challenges (in translating industrial questions into STEM tractable blocks):

- Is the challenge modellable?
 - Raising awareness of techniques.
 - Breakdown the model into problems.
- Identifying the right technique (AI can have a role here – look up by key words and relating them to specific areas and useful techniques – auto-translation. Can we ensure consistency?)
 - Balancing advantages and disadvantages as pros and cons.
 - Lessons learnt – negative results – what we tried and didn't work and why it didn't.
 - Techniques – applies to Modelling Challenges.
 - How to make a start?
 - What are the key inputs, key variables, initial or boundary conditions, etc.
 - Awareness of resource requirements (compute, data, research effort).
 - Awareness of key data availability to put an initial or boundary conditions in?
 - What does output mean?
 - Calculation a property v/s improving understanding, what is the accuracy?
 - Formats conversion tools and community standards.
 - In VVUQ we trust.
 - Timescales
 - Are we working at the right length- and time-scales for the phenomena being investigated?
 - How long does it take and to what level confidence, i.e., associate the activity with risk in a business context?
 - Is it quicker to use another, less accurate technique (multiscale, Multiphysics, etc.)?
- Good link to experts (one expert cannot be good at everything).

- What is the role of AI? Great but how general purpose is it and what does it help learn?
- Do we need a translator (ecosystem) as a BID may complicate things (communication, relationship, time to solution barrier)?
- Digitalisation requires change of management – it's a digital journey, requiring moving away from traditional approaches (learn by yourself). This is a key for general digital education (targeted training, coaching, collaboration).

Main Modelling Challenges

- Reliable/Robust Coarse Grained (multiscale/multiphysics) methods.
- Links back to atomistic systems or to macroscopic continuum.
- Applying AI/ML to limited, sparse, incomplete, varied in density and dimensions datasets.
- Transferability of parameters/models/potentials/interactions away from the training space/sets.
- Ease-of-use for software, flexibility (moving to other alternatives for the same methodology).
- Mixing different FF, especially organic-inorganic interfaces/interactions.
- Data management challenges:
 - Enabling collaboration between experiment and simulation.
 - Standardisation. Metadata and semantisation.
 - Recovery, repeatability, VVUQ.
- Use of experimental data to verify (CG) simulations/FF.
- Moving up and down scales.
- Selection of FFs and comments on compatibility, flexibility, transferability.

The Role of AI/ML

We consider only physics-based ML. That is usually based on building some order parameter (collective variables) – based on some pre-knowledge of the molecular system. Usual applications are related to phase transitions (in colloids). Further applications are possible in generating MLed PES as a substitute to classical potentials for atomistic interactions. ML can be used to validate data.

Challenges to Industry (from the viewpoint of industrial R&D leads and researchers)

- Lack of translation and pre-translation (capability/how many as diversity of areas and capacity/how much as many times time).
- Lack of data – classification with links to providers (linkage to PSDI).
- Lack of a general portal with methods classification and links to offerings.
- Interests in product stability (time to failure, minimising side reactions, maximising yield, coupling to by-product pathways).
- Unclear about reactor conditions – modelling methods have specificity whereas reactor conditions are 'ambient' and 'average'. Connection from fixed conditions to a reactive/engineering flow/processing.
- Whole scale, many states along a reaction or rather many states of different reaction pathways. How many pathways are needed to represent realistically an chemical engineering scenario?
- High-throughput scanning needed for the type of problems (conditions/reactions).
- Vitrex inspired challenges – molecular design, polymer reactions, dielectric constant calculation, electric response, electrical properties, fracture, degradation chemistry (colour), circular economy.

General Conclusions

Theme: Communication, interaction, contacts and matchmaking, blogging, fora

- General need of Community Hub (Marketplace of experts), linking to a community forum.
- Lack of a general portal with methods/data classification and links to offerings.
- A match making service – Challenges to Champions (can be a portal/marketplace/forum).
- Value in learning from others – do, don'ts, blogs (forum facility).
- FORUM – a suggestion of the EMMC ASBL one as an impartial (outside the public funding) place of practitioners, <https://emmc.eu/forum/>, requires registration (with associate free and paid membership partitions).

Theme: Access to data, standards, interoperability/conversion tools and best practices across communities

- Data access, standards, curation services.
- Needs for interoperability and format conversion tools.
- Cross-community standards.

Theme: Digital guides for beginners

- Awareness of techniques – digital guides for beginners, linking to the ALC Digital Guides project.

Theme: The value of AI needs clarification

- Role of AI can be very cross-cutting but ultimately depends the data availability and quality for the questions asked. No AI Hubs of knowledge and too many pockets of varied application.

Theme: Pathways to matchmaking

- CCP5++ is a vehicle for thematic workshops as collaborative opportunities and accessing experts. Hackathons. The Royce Institute also has similar offerings. PSDI workshops. Target workshops to match “problems to champions”.

Identified Needs

Engaging “new players” with modelling science requires access to flexible workforce as it is not possible to employ people full time; also showcasing outcomes may be too slow, especially if a company is after access to proof of concept. Possible instruments of co-funding or full support should be considered – there are two within Hartree's and Royce's scope:

- Appoint application scientists in one of Royce spokes (junior-mid career post-docs) to deploy rapidly on proof-of-concept computational work. This is essentially a de-risking activity.
- Support for financial "sprint" projects (e.g., 3-6 months) where expert and company design a feasibility study or address a narrow model question. In this case the scientists carrying out the work can be anywhere in the UK and are seconded from different project/institution.

Complementary Information (captured via sli.do)

Questions:

1. How transferable are coarse grained force-fields - how much experimental benchmarking is required to be sure they can be applied in different situations.
2. Do you use uncertainty in predicted properties or models to determine how applicable your methods are compared to experiments?
3. How transferable are coarse grained force-fields - how much experimental benchmarking is required to be sure they can be applied in different situations.
4. Is there a preference for accuracy of predicted properties compared to chemical/physical insights on the processes or are both of equal importance?
5. How do you interpret the ML models i.e., are there specific methods?
6. Are there plans to publish the EELS spectra datasets?
7. How much data was required to reproduce the phase diagrams?
8. What are the challenges with selecting a particular ML model and what are the potential pitfalls.
9. What are the options for application of ML techniques to computationally challenging species e.g., actinides.
10. Kaggle for materials modelling / asynchronous modelling capability sharing?

Challenges:

- The circular economy...when I recover and recycle a material, usually by the application of heat and pressure, some level of degradation inevitably results. I have some idea of the degradation chemistry, but not completely. Repeated recycling ultimately results in a material which is no longer fit for use due to loss of mechanical properties (brittleness, loss of toughness or ductility), change of colour (from light to dark). I need a model which can relate the type and degree of chemical degradation to the macroscopic properties of the material. Can you help?
- How to relate the fracture toughness, crazing behaviour and fatigue performance of a material to its molecular structure, which in turn may be influenced by how it has been processed to achieve that molecular structure?
- How to predict the electrical properties, e.g., dielectric constant, PDIV, dielectric strength of polymeric insulating materials?
- Predicting chemical reactions in the presence of competing reactions / side reactions and optimising conditions so as to achieve the maximum yield of the desired product whilst minimising by products.
- To drive adoption of new materials durable applications, end users need confidence they will last in the environments in which they will be used, otherwise they won't use them. How can you model how a material (or multi material system, like a composite) will behave/perform in the presence of various chemicals, cyclic loading, pressure and temperature changes, etc.?
- Machine learning.
- New materials discovery and development.

Next Steps:

Dr. Wei Wu

Many thanks for this fantastic workshop.

- Regarding marketplace, UCL has been contributing to the EU Marketplace project and responsible for developing translation services platform. For the moment, the project has

an online platform for translation services under test, for which I am a co-developer (notice that the platform subject to further improvement). From my opinion, this kind of translation services not only need computer screening but also human interventions. I think it might be appropriate for the materials modellers and industries involved in this workshop to try out the platform and provide your valuable and critical feedbacks. In the meantime, this would benefit further ccp5 workshop?

Otello M Roscioni

- On future meetings, I'd like to see challenges from industry and discuss what are the most cost-effective methods to address them (I acknowledge Tom for raising this point).

Figure 1. Left – Q&A session participants’ output collected via a sli.do session. Left-side) word-cloud of the most mentioned words. Right-side) submitted and ranked focus areas of challenges.

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